

AIRBORNE
LABORATORY

FAAM ARINC708 Weather Radar Processing

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INTRODUCTION

The FAAM aircraft is equipped with a Honeywell RDR-4B X-band Doppler weather radar. The radar is an aircraft system, used for weather detection and avoidance. While the radar is primarily used for weather detection, it may also be of interest to scientists after the flight during data analysis. The radar system has been extended to include the ability for mission scientists to view radar data independently of the cockpit display.

Fig. 1.1: The Honeywell RDR-4B Doppler weather radar, and an example of the MS display.

Each scan provides 512 bins between the aircraft and the current range limit, categorized using an integer code between 0 and 7, along with information such as tilt, scan angle, range and gain. The radar data is stored as a binary file, which is then converted to netCDF format for easier analysis, using this software. During the conversion, the range, tilt, scan angle and gain are converted from bit representation to physical units.

THE ARINC708 PROTOCOL

Weather radar data is transmitted using the ARINC708 protocol. The ARINC708 word consists of a 64-bit header and a 512 data values of 3 bits each. The full word is thus 1600 bits long.

Note: ARINC data are presented LSB first, so the first bit transmitted is the least significant bit of the first byte.

2.1 The Header

The 64 bit header starts with a label of 8 bits, which is always 0o055 (or equivalently 0b10110100). The header contains the following fields:

Table 2.1: ARINC708 Header

Bit(s)	Name	Description
0-7	Label	Always 0o055
8-9	Control Accept	See Table 2.2
10	Slave	0=Master, 1=Slave
11-12	Unused	
13-17	Mode Annunciation	See Table 2.3
18-24	Faults	See Table 2.4
25	Stabilization	0=Off, 1=On
26-28	Operating Mode	See Table 2.5
29-35	Tilt	See Table 2.6
36-41	Gain	See Table 2.7
42-47	Range	See Table 2.8
48	Unused	
49-50	Data Accept	See Table 2.9
51-62	Scan angle	See <i>Scan Angle</i>
63	Unused	

2.1.1 Control Accept

Table 2.2: Control Accept

Bit 9	Bit 8	Description
0	0	Do not accept control
0	1	IND1 accept control
1	0	IND2 accept control
1	1	IND1 and IND2 accept control

2.1.2 Mode Annunciation

Table 2.3: Mode Annunciation

Bit	Mode annunciation
13	Automatic sensing of a turbulence alert has occurred
14	Automatic sensing of a reflectivity weather alert has occurred
15	Clutter elimination is active
16	Reduced sector scan is in operation
17	Aircraft attitude and/or tilt exceeds the system's design limits

2.1.3 Faults

Table 2.4: Faults

Bit	Fault
18	Cooling fault
19	Display fault
20	Calibration fault
21	Altitude input fault
22	Control fault
23	Antenna fault
24	Transmitter/receiver fault

2.1.4 Operating Mode

Table 2.5: Operating Mode

Bit 28	Bit 27	Bit 26	Operating mode
0	0	0	Standby
0	0	1	Weather (only)
0	1	0	Map
0	1	1	Contour
1	0	0	Test
1	0	1	Turbulence (only)
1	1	0	Weather and turbulence
1	1	1	Reserved (Calibration annunciation)

2.1.5 Tilt

Table 2.6: Tilt

Bit	Tilt (degrees)
35	-16
34	+8
33	+4
32	+2
31	+1
30	+0.5
29	+0.25

2.1.6 Gain

Table 2.7: Gain

Bit 41	Bit 40	Bit 39	Bit 38	Bit 37	Bit 36	Gain (dB)
1	1	1	1	1	1	Calibration
0	0	0	0	0	0	Max
0	0	0	0	0	1	-5
0	0	0	0	1	1	-11
1	1	1	1	1	0	-62

2.1.7 Range

Table 2.8: Range

Bit 47	Bit 46	Bit 45	Bit 44	Bit 43	Bit 42	Range (nm)
0	0	0	0	0	1	5
0	0	0	0	1	0	10
0	0	0	1	0	0	20
0	0	1	0	0	0	40
0	1	0	0	0	0	80
1	0	0	0	0	0	160
1	1	1	1	1	1	315
0	0	0	0	0	0	320

2.1.8 Data Accept

Table 2.9: Data Accept

Bit 50	Bit 49	Data Accept
0	0	Do not accept data
0	1	Accept data 1
1	0	Accept data 2
1	1	Accept any data

2.1.9 Scan Angle

The scan angle is given by bits 51-62. Bit 62 is the most significant bit, and takes a value of 180 degrees. Each less significant bit takes the value of half the next more significant bit. For example, bit 61 takes a value of 90 degrees, and bit 60 takes a value of 45 degrees. The least significant bit, bit 51, takes a value of 0.087890625 degrees.

2.2 The Data

The data payload is 1536 bits long, divided into 512 3-bit fields. Each field gives a categorized radar return, summarized in [Table 2.10](#).

Table 2.10: Data bins

Bit 2	Bit 1	Bit 0	Category	Representative Color
0	0	0	No precipitation (<Z2)	Black
0	0	1	Light precipitation (Z2 to Z3)	Green
0	1	0	Moderate precipitation (Z3 to Z4)	Yellow
0	1	1	Heavy precipitation (Z4 to Z5)	Red
1	0	0	Very heavy precipitation (>Z5)	Magenta
1	0	1	Reserved (out of cal indication)	
1	1	0	Medium turbulence	
1	1	1	Heavy turbulence	

DATASET DESCRIPTION

The FAAM provided weather radar data are provided in a netCDF file. The file is essentially a low-level representation of the raw aring data, with the exception of the following:

- Range (nm)
- Tilt (deg)
- Gain (dB)
- Scan angle (deg)

which are all converted from their packed binary representation to floating point or integer values.

A full description of the data format is provided in the [FAAM Data Github repository](#). For convenience, a summary of the data format is provided below.

3.1 WxRx NetCDF Specification

3.1.1 Global Attributes

- Conventions: CF-1.9 ACDD-1.3
- acknowledgement: Airborne data was obtained using the BAe-146-301 Atmospheric Research Aircraft [ARA] flown by Airtask Ltd and managed by FAAM Airborne Laboratory, jointly operated by UKRI and the University of Leeds
- creator_address: Building 146, Cranfield University, College Road, Cranfield, Bedford. MK43 0AL. UK.
- creator_email: <str: derived_from_file>
- creator_institution: FAAM Airborne Laboratory
- creator_name: <str: derived_from_file>
- creator_type: institution
- date: <str: derived_from_file>
- date_created: <str: derived_from_file>
- flight_date: <str: derived_from_file>
- flight_number: <str: derived_from_file>
- geospatial_bounds: <str: derived_from_file>
- geospatial_bounds_crs: EPSG:4979
- geospatial_lat_min: <float32: derived_from_file>
- geospatial_lat_units: degree_north
- geospatial_lat_max: <float32: derived_from_file>

- `geospatial_lon_min`: <float32: derived_from_file>
- `geospatial_lon_max`: <float32: derived_from_file>
- `geospatial_lon_units`: `degree_east`
- `geospatial_vertical_min`: <float32: derived_from_file>
- `geospatial_vertical_max`: <float32: derived_from_file>
- `geospatial_vertical_units`: `m`
- `geospatial_vertical_positive`: `up`
- `id`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `institution`: `FAAM Airborne Laboratory`
- `keywords`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `keywords_vocabulary`: `Global Change Master Directory (GCMD)`
- `license`: `UK Government Open Licence agreement - http://www.nationalarchives.gov.uk/doc/open-government-licence`
- `metadata_link`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `naming_authority`: `uk.ac.faam`
- `platform`: `FAAM BAe-146-301 Atmospheric Research Aircraft`
- `platform_type`: `aircraft`
- `project`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `publisher_email`: `support@ceda.ac.uk`
- `publisher_institution`: `CEDA`
- `publisher_type`: `institution`
- `publisher_url`: `https://www.ceda.ac.uk`
- `references`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `revision_date`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `revision_number`: <int32: derived_from_file>
- `source`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `standard_name_vocabulary`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `summary`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `time_coverage_duration`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `time_coverage_start`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `time_coverage_end`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `title`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `uuid`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `comment`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `creator_url`: `https://www.faam.ac.uk`
- `processing_software_doi`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `processing_software_url`: `https://github.com/faam-146/faam-wrx`
- `processing_software_version`: <str: derived_from_file>
- `project_acronym`: <str: derived_from_file>

- project_name: <str: derived_from_file>
- project_principal_investigator: <str: derived_from_file>
- project_principal_investigator_email: <str: derived_from_file>
- project_principal_investigator_url: <str: derived_from_file>

3.1.2 Dimensions

- time: unlimited
- bins: 512

3.1.3 Variables

- time
 - datatype: <int32>
 - dimensions: time
 - attributes:
 - * _FillValue: -9999
 - * coverage_content_type: *coordinate*
 - * frequency: 0
 - * long_name: *Time of scan line estimated from data size*
 - * units: *seconds since 1970-01-01 00:00:00*
 - * calendar: *gregorian*
- control_accept
 - datatype: <int8>
 - dimensions: time
 - attributes:
 - * _FillValue: -128
 - * coverage_content_type: *auxiliaryInformation*
 - * frequency: 0
 - * long_name: *Control Acceptance Indicator*
 - * units: 1
 - * valid_max: 3.0
 - * valid_min: 0.0
- slave
 - datatype: <int8>
 - dimensions: time
 - attributes:
 - * _FillValue: -128
 - * coverage_content_type: *auxiliaryInformation*
 - * frequency: 0

- * long_name: *Slave Indicator*
- * units: *1*
- * comment: *0=Master, 1=Slave*
- * valid_max: *1.0*
- * valid_min: *0.0*
- mode_annunciation
 - datatype: *<int8>*
 - dimensions: *time*
 - attributes:
 - * _FillValue: *-128*
 - * coverage_content_type: *auxiliaryInformation*
 - * frequency: *0*
 - * long_name: *Mode Annunciation, packed*
 - * units: *1*
 - * comment: *Each bit represents a mode annunciation. See documentation for details.*
 - * valid_max: *31.0*
 - * valid_min: *0.0*
- faults
 - datatype: *<int8>*
 - dimensions: *time*
 - attributes:
 - * _FillValue: *-128*
 - * coverage_content_type: *auxiliaryInformation*
 - * frequency: *0*
 - * long_name: *Fault Flags, packed*
 - * units: *1*
 - * comment: *Each bit represents a fault indication. See documentation for details.*
 - * valid_max: *127.0*
 - * valid_min: *0.0*
- stabilization
 - datatype: *<int8>*
 - dimensions: *time*
 - attributes:
 - * _FillValue: *-128*
 - * coverage_content_type: *auxiliaryInformation*
 - * frequency: *0*
 - * long_name: *Stabilization Indicator*
 - * units: *1*
 - * comment: *0=Off, 1=On*

- * valid_max: 1.0
- * valid_min: 0.0
- operating_mode
 - datatype: <int8>
 - dimensions: time
 - attributes:
 - * _FillValue: -128
 - * coverage_content_type: *auxiliaryInformation*
 - * frequency: 0
 - * long_name: *Operating Mode*
 - * units: 1
 - * valid_max: 7.0
 - * valid_min: 0.0
- tilt
 - datatype: <float32>
 - dimensions: time
 - attributes:
 - * _FillValue: -9999
 - * coverage_content_type: *auxiliaryInformation*
 - * frequency: 0
 - * long_name: *Radar tilt angle*
 - * units: *degree*
 - * valid_max: 15.75
 - * valid_min: -16.0
- gain
 - datatype: <int8>
 - dimensions: time
 - attributes:
 - * _FillValue: -9999
 - * coverage_content_type: *auxiliaryInformation*
 - * frequency: 0
 - * long_name: *Gain*
 - * units: *dB*
 - * comment: *A value of 0 indicates maximum gain. A value of 1 indicates calibration.*
 - * valid_max: 1.0
 - * valid_min: -62.0
- range
 - datatype: <int16>
 - dimensions: time

- attributes:
 - * `_FillValue`: -9999
 - * `coverage_content_type`: *auxiliaryInformation*
 - * `frequency`: 0
 - * `long_name`: *Range from aircraft*
 - * `units`: 1
 - * `comment`: *Represents the maximum range bin*
 - * `valid_max`: 320.0
 - * `valid_min`: 5.0
- `data_accept`
 - datatype: `<int8>`
 - dimensions: time
 - attributes:
 - * `_FillValue`: -128
 - * `coverage_content_type`: *auxiliaryInformation*
 - * `frequency`: 0
 - * `long_name`: *Data Accept Indicator*
 - * `units`: 1
 - * `valid_max`: 3.0
 - * `valid_min`: 0.0
- `scan_angle`
 - datatype: `<float32>`
 - dimensions: time
 - attributes:
 - * `_FillValue`: -128
 - * `coverage_content_type`: *auxiliaryInformation*
 - * `frequency`: 0
 - * `long_name`: *Radar Scan Angle*
 - * `units`: 1
 - * `comment`: *The scan angle is the angle between the aircraft and the center of the radar beam.*
 - * `valid_max`: 359.912109375
 - * `valid_min`: 0.0
- `reflectivity`
 - datatype: `<int8>`
 - dimensions: time, bins
 - attributes:
 - * `_FillValue`: -128
 - * `coverage_content_type`: *thematicClassification*
 - * `frequency`: 0

* long_name: *Categorized reflectivity data*

* units: *1*

* valid_max: *7.0*

* valid_min: *0.0*

CODE REFERENCE

4.1 wxrx.read_wrx

`wrx.read_wrx.load_tmp_file(filename: str) → bytes`

Load a raw ARINC 708 file.

Parameters

filename (*str*) – The filename of the raw ARINC 708 file

Returns

The raw ARINC 708 data

Return type

bytes

`wrx.read_wrx.parse_message(data: bytes) → Arinc708Message`

Parse a single ARINC 708 message. See the ARINC 708 specification for details.

Parameters

data (*bytes*) – The data to parse

Returns

The parsed message

Return type

Arinc708Message

`wrx.read_wrx.process(tempfiles: list[str], logfile: str, corefile: str, with_progress: bool = True) → None`

Process a list of raw ARINC 708 files and write the output to a NetCDF file.

Parameters

- **tempfiles** (*list[str]*) – A list of raw ARINC 708 files
- **logfile** (*str*) – The filename of the log file
- **corefile** (*str*) – The filename of the core file
- **with_progress** (*bool*) – Whether to show a progress bar. Defaults to True.

`wrx.read_wrx.process_tmp_file(data: bytes, tempfile: str, t: Timer, nc: NetCDFWriter, pbar: tqdm | None = None)`

Process a single raw ARINC 708 file and write the output to a NetCDF file.

Parameters

- **data** (*bytes*) – The raw ARINC 708 data
- **tempfile** (*str*) – The filename of the raw ARINC 708 file
- **t** (*Timer*) – The timer object, used to convert the index of the message to a timestamp
- **nc** (*NetCDFWriter*) – The NetCDF writer object

- **pbar** (*tqdm/None*) – The progress bar object

`wrx.read_wrx.scan_tmp_data(data: bytes) → Generator[tuple[int, wxrx.arinc.Arinc708Message], None, None]`

Scan a raw ARINC 708 file and yield each message.

Parameters

data (*bytes*) – The raw ARINC 708 data

Yields

tuple[int, Arinc708Message] – The index of the message and the message

4.2 wxrx.converters

`wrx.converters.gain_from_int(i: int) → int`

Returns the gain. A value of 0 indicates maximum gain. A value of 1 indicates calibration.

May raise a `KeyError` if the gain is not in the lookup table.

Parameters

i (*int*) – The encoded gain value.

Returns

The gain, or an indicator of calibration.

Return type

`int`

`wrx.converters.range_from_int(i: int) → int`

Returns the range in nautical miles. A value of 0 indicates maximum range, 320 nautical miles.

May raise a `KeyError` if the range is not in the lookup table.

Parameters

i (*int*) – The encoded range value.

Returns

The range in nautical miles.

Return type

`int`

`wrx.converters.scan_angle_from_int(i: int) → float`

Returns the scan angle from the integer representation.

Parameters

i (*int*) – The integer representation of the scan angle.

Returns

The scan angle in degrees.

Return type

`float`

`wrx.converters.tilt_from_int(i: int) → float`

Returns the tilt angle in degrees.

Parameters

i (*int*) – The encoded tilt value.

Returns

The tilt angle in degrees.

Return type

`float`

4.3 wxrx.netcdf

`wrxrx.netcdf.GLOBAL_OVERWRITES(writer: NetCDFWriter) → dict[str, Any]`

Get the global attributes for the netCDF file which are not defined in the product definition or in the core file.

class `wrxrx.netcdf.NetCDFWriter(corefile: str)`

Bases: object

A class to write a netCDF file from the ARINC708 databus weather radar data.

`__init__(corefile: str) → None`

Create a new NetCDFWriter object.

Parameters

corefile (*str*) – Path to the core file to use for the metadata

`init_file()` → None

Initialise the netCDF file, creating the dimensions and variables from the product definition.

`write_message(time: float, message: Arinc708Message) → None`

Write a single ARINC708 message to the netCDF file.

Parameters

- **time** (*float*) – Time of the message, in seconds since the epoch
- **message** (*Arinc708Message*) – The ARINC708 message to write

`wrxrx.netcdf.get_duration(start_time: datetime, end_time: datetime) → str`

Get the duration of the flight in ISO8601 format

Parameters

- **start_time** (*datetime.datetime*) – Start time of the flight
- **end_time** (*datetime.datetime*) – End time of the flight

Returns

Duration of the flight in ISO8601 format

Return type

str

4.4 wxrx.timer

class `wrxrx.timer.Timer(logfile: str, tmpfile: str = "")`

Bases: object

Provides a timer for a given logfile and tmpfile. This allows the time at which a given size was reached to be calculated. This is used to add a timestamp to the ARINC708 data, which is not timestamped.

`__init__(logfile: str, tmpfile: str = "") → None`

Create a new Timer object.

Parameters

- **logfile** (*str*) – Path to the logfile to use for the timer
- **tmpfile** (*str*) – The tmpfile to use for the timer.

property date: date

Returns the date of the first entry in the logfile.

Returns

The date of the first entry in the logfile

Return type

datetime.date

includes(*tempfile: str*) → bool

Indicates whether the timer includes a reference to the given tempfile.

Parameters

tempfile (*str*) – The tempfile to check for

Returns

True if the timer includes the tempfile, False otherwise

Return type

bool

time_at_size(*size: int, tempfile: str = ""*) → Timestamp

Returns the time at which the given size was reached.

Parameters

- **size** (*int*) – The size to check for
- **tempfile** (*str*) – The tempfile to check for

Returns

The nearest time to which the given size was reached.

Return type

pd.Timestamp

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